

Recent development of Brønsted acid-promoted synthesis of quinoline, isoquinoline and carboline derivatives[†]

K. C. Majumdar* and Sudipta Ponra

Department of Chemistry, University of Kalyani, Kalyani-741 235, West Bengal, India

E-mail : kcm@klyuniv.ac.in Fax : 91-33-25828282

Manuscript received 04 March 2013, accepted 07 March 2013

Abstract : Various quinolines, isoquinolines and carbolines-based natural and unnatural products can be synthesized by Brønsted acid-promoted cyclization. We have made an attempt to summarize the progress made in this area during the period 2005 to date. This article describes the synthetic routes to these heterocycles that involve a Brønsted acid-promoted cyclization as a crucial step or a Brønsted acid as a co-catalysts with other transition metals.

Keywords : Quinolines, isoquinolines, carbolines, Brønsted acid-promoted cyclization, chiral phosphoric acid, co-catalysts.

Introduction

Brønsted acid-promoted reactions are very useful because these acids are cheap, readily available, easy to handle and efficiently catalyze the intramolecular addition of oxygen and nitrogen nucleophiles to alkynes, allenes, and olefins to generate oxygen and nitrogen heterocycles. Among various nitrogen heterocycles quinoline, isoquinoline and carbolines-based natural and unnatural products can be synthesized by Brønsted acid-promoted cyclization.

The discovery of quinoline in 1842 by Gerhardt as the result of drastic decomposition of quinine and of cinchonine antedates Anderson's discovery of pyridine by four years. Quinolines and their derivatives are of great importance owing to their wide occurrence in natural products¹ and biologically active compounds². A large variety of quinolines display interesting physiological activities and found attractive applications as pharmaceuticals and agrochemicals, as well as general synthetic building blocks^{1b}. To date, a number of quinoline-containing compounds have been successfully commercialized, such as Singulair, Tafenoquine, Aldara and Hydroxychloroquine³. Substituted quinoline have also been employed as ligands for the preparation of OLED phosphorescent complexes⁴ and organocatalysts for enantioselective synthesis of chiral

molecules⁵. The synthesis of quinoline by Skraup was perhaps the greatest single momentum to its further study. Not only quinoline is readily available from easily accessible materials, but also a host of substituted products could be as readily obtained. Many synthetic methods (Scheme 1) such as Skraup, Doebner-von Miller, Friedländer, Combes reactions have been developed for the preparation of quinolines⁶. But due to their great importance, the development of novel synthetic approaches remains an active research area⁷.

Scheme 1. Various methods for quinoline synthesis.

[†]In honour of Professor Sunil Kumar Talapatra on the occasion of his 80th birthday.

Quinoline derivatives

Friedländer annulation^{8a,b}, an acid- or base-catalyzed condensation, followed by a cyclodehydration between an aromatic 2-aminoaldehyde or ketone and a carbonyl compound containing a reactive α -methylene group, is one of the most simple and straightforward approaches for the synthesis of polysubstituted quinolines. Wang *et al.* used Friedländer condensation of 2-aminoarylketone or 2-aminoarylaldehyde **1** with carbonyl compounds **2** in the presence of *para*-toluene sulphonic acid for rapid and efficient preparation of various poly-substituted quinolines **3**⁹. The reaction is equally efficient under both microwave irradiation and conventional heating under solvent-free conditions (Scheme 2). The same reaction for the synthesis of substituted quinoline derivatives **3** (Scheme 3) in the presence of hydrochloric acid utilizing water as the solvent at 60 °C has also been described by the same group¹⁰. Shaabani *et al.* used trifluoroacetic acid as an efficient catalyst for the Friedländer synthesis of quinoline derivatives (Scheme 4)¹¹.

Scheme 2. *p*-TSA-mediated synthesis of poly-substituted quinoline derivatives.

Scheme 3. HCl-mediated synthesis of poly-substituted quinoline derivatives.

Scheme 4. Trifluoroacetic acid-mediated quinoline synthesis.

Dai and co-workers established^{12a} the microwave reaction conditions for the $\text{CF}_3\text{CO}_2\text{H}$ -catalyzed three-component aza-Diels-Alder reaction involving 2-aminophenols

as the amine building blocks for the synthesis of highly functionalized 8-hydroxy-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroquinolines **12** and **13** in 39–59% isolated yields and in 36:64–16:84 diastereomeric ratios in favor of the *trans*-isomers (Scheme 5). The microwave-heated three-component aza-Diels-Alder reactions were completed in significantly reduced reaction time to give the same level of chemical yield and diastereomeric ratio as obtained from the room temperature reaction. Similarly Liu and co-workers used HCl-ethanol for the efficient synthesis of furano[3,2-*c*]quinoline derivatives^{12b}.

Another $\text{CF}_3\text{CO}_2\text{H}$ -catalyzed aza-Diels-Alder reaction for the synthesis of 6*H*-chromeno[4,3-*b*]quinolines **15** has been reported by Tomashevskaya *et al.*¹³. The dienes (Schiff bases) for aza-Diels-Alder reactions were generated *in situ* from the substituted anilines **14** and 2-allyloxybenzaldehyde **15** (Scheme 6).

DeShong *et al.* used acid-catalyzed Meyer-Schuster Rearrangement/Heteroannulation for the synthesis of 2-substituted and 2,4-disubstituted quinoline derivatives **18**¹⁴. Reduction of secondary and tertiary *o*-nitrophenyl propargyl alcohols **17**, followed by acid-catalyzed Meyer-Schuster rearrangement, gave the quinoline derivatives (Scheme 7). Tertiary propargyl alcohols gave excellent yields, while secondary propargyl alcohol was found to give slightly lower yield of quinoline derivatives. The methodology tolerates both electron-donating and electron-withdrawing functionality on A-ring and the substitution on the alkyne part. It was observed that Zn-, Fe- and Sn-reductions generally gave excellent yields. The proposed mechanism is depicted in Scheme 8.

Polycyclic quinolines **20** can be synthesized via palladium-catalyzed chemoselective arylamination of β -bromovinylaldehydes **19** with aromatic amines, followed by acid-catalyzed cyclization with trifluoroacetic acid (Scheme 9)¹⁵.

Zhu *et al.* developed¹⁶ a sulfuric acid-mediated efficient protocol for the synthesis of 4-alkoxy-2-arylquinolines **22** by heating a mixture of easily accessible 2-(2-(trimethylsilyl)ethynyl)anilines **21** and aromatic aldehydes **10** in alcoholic solvents (Scheme 10). The aromatic aldehydes with electron-donating groups or halogens gave moderate to good yields (61–81%). However, electron-deficient aldehydes provided much lower yields. No de-

Scheme 5. Microwave-assisted synthesis of highly functionalized 1,2,3,4-tetrahydroquinoline derivatives.

Scheme 6. Synthesis of 6H-chromeno[4,3-*b*]quinolines derivatives.

Scheme 7. Synthesis of 2-substituted and 2,4-disubstituted quinoline derivatives.

sired product was obtained when strong electron-deficient 4-nitrobenzaldehyde and 2-pyridinecarboxaldehyde were used as substrates. The major by-products in these cases were corresponding methoxyacetals. The reaction was also unfavorable with the sterically hindered substrates. Electron-rich heteroaromatic aldehydes were suitable substrates for this reaction. 2'-Aminoacetophenone **23** was isolated in 83% yield under the same reaction condition in the

Scheme 8. Proposed mechanism : Resonance-stabilised Meyer-Schuster Rearrangement/Heteroannulation.

Scheme 9. Synthesis of polycyclic quinoline derivatives.

Scheme 10. Synthesis of 4-alkoxy-2-arylquinoline derivatives.

absence of the aldehyde (Scheme 11). But the yield of **22** was much lower (49%) when **23** was used instead of **21** as a substrate. This result suggests the mechanism shown in Scheme 12, that involves: (1) imine formation under acid catalysis, (2) intramolecular attack of the alkyne to iminium **A**, (3) the resulting vinyl cation **B** quenched by methanol and finally (4) desilylation and air oxidation of 1,2-dihydroquinoline **C** to give the final product **22**.

corresponding 10-methoxyphenyl-3*H*-pyrano[3,2-*f*]quinolin-3-one derivatives **26** by $\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in methanol (Scheme 14). The substrate **24** was treated with various aromatic aldehydes **10** under the optimized condition to give cyclized products **25** in 18–75% yields. When *ortho*-substituted aromatic aldehydes were used, the yields of the products were drastically reduced. This is perhaps due to steric effect. Presence of bulky group at the *ortho*-

Scheme 11. Stepwise synthesis of 4-methoxy-2-phenylquinolines.

Scheme 12. Proposed mechanism for the acid-promoted cyclization.

We have developed a new efficient and simple route for the synthesis of 8,9-dihydro-3*H*-pyrano[3,2-*f*]quinoline-3,10(7*H*)-dione derivatives **25** by sulfuric acid-promoted condensation-cyclization of 6-amino-5-((trimethylsilyl)ethynyl)-2*H*-chromen-2-ones **24** and aromatic aldehydes **10** (Scheme 13)¹⁷. The products can be oxidized to the

Scheme 13. Synthesis of 8,9-dihydro-3*H*-pyrano[3,2-*f*]quinoline-3,10(7*H*)-dione.

Scheme 14. Synthesis of 10-methoxyphenyl-3*H*-pyrano[3,2-*f*]quinolin-3-one derivatives.

position may prevent cyclization towards the product formation. The desired product was not obtained when strong electron-deficient 3- or 4-nitrobenzaldehyde was used as aromatic aldehyde. The reaction of aliphatic aldehydes also did not afford the desired cyclized product. A complex mixture of products was obtained when the reaction was attempted by replacing the TMS group in substrate **24** with a phenyl group using this protocol.

Two different pathways ('Pathway a' and 'Pathway b') may be considered for the formation of the products **5a-l** from the substrates **3** (Scheme 15). The acid-catalyzed hydration of the TMS-alkynes (**24**) supported the β -silylation effect may lead to enols **27** (under acidic conditions) that may be followed by a sequence of Mannich reaction with the iminium ion to give products **25** ('Pathway a'). Alternatively, initial step may be the formation of iminium ions **28** by the condensation of amine **24** and aromatic aldehydes **10** in the presence of acid, which may then undergo cyclization to form the vinyl cations **29**. The vinyl cations **29** may react with water and subsequent removal of a proton may give the enols **30**. The intermediate enol forms **30** may readily get converted to the products **32**, the more stable tautomer. Removal of MeOTMS (when R' = TMS) from **32** may give the final products **25**. Compounds **31** were not obtained perhaps due to the fact that tautomeric conversion to **32** is much faster than the aerial oxidation (aromatization) of **30** ('Pathway b').

Gestwicki and Evans reported a four-component Hantzsch condensation reaction of dimedone **33**, ethyl acetoacetate **34**, aromatic aldehydes **10**, and ammonium acetate **35** catalyzed by chiral phosphoric acid **36**, giving the desired quinoline derivatives **37** in good yields with high enantioselectivities (Scheme 16)¹⁸. Similarly, 1-(4-sulfonic acid)butyl-3-methylimidazolium hydrogen sulfate ($[(\text{CH}_2)_4\text{SO}_3\text{HMIM}][\text{HSO}_4]$), a Brønsted acid ionic liquid, can efficiently catalyze the same reaction¹⁹.

Zhang and co-workers used *p*-TSA as a co-catalyst for convenient one-pot synthesis of 2,3-disubstituted, 2,3,6-trisubstituted, and 2,3,6,7-tetrasubstituted quinoline analogues **39** from terminal alkynes **38** via sequential ruthenium(II) and *para*-toluenesulfonic acid (*p*-TSA) co-catalyzed reactions (Scheme 17)²⁰. The catalytic process is shown to take place first via intermediate formation of an allyl ketone and then addition of an aniline derivative to the allyl ketone. *p*-TSA is a catalyst for both allyl ketone and quinoline synthetic steps. The method is very useful to synthesize a wide range of quinoline derivatives and introduce different substituents by employing various simple starting materials. The reaction allows the synthesis of halogen-containing products.

Manoj and Prasad reported that the reaction of 2,4-dichloroquinolines (**40**) with equal or excess moles of *o*-aminoacetophenone and *o*-aminobenzophenone (**1**) resulted only in the formation of monosubstituted anilinoquinolines

Scheme 15. Probable mechanism for condensation cyclization reaction.

Scheme 16. Hantzsch condensation.

Scheme 17. *p*-TSA-co-catalyzed synthesis of substituted quinoline derivatives.

41. The acid-catalyzed internal electrophilic cyclization reaction of **41** with PPA at 205–210 °C yielded the respective 6-substituted dibenzo[*b,g*][1,8]naphthyridin-5-one (**42**) in 17–33% yield (Scheme 18)²¹.

In the year 2011, Pisaneschi *et al.* reported the synthesis of a range of 2-substituted 2,3-dihydro-1*H* quinolin-4-ones **44** via acid-catalyzed cyclization of 2-(3'-

hydroxypropynyl)anilines **43** (Scheme 19)²². The cyclization reaction appears to proceed via regioselective rearrangement of the propargyl alcohol to an α,β -unsaturated ketone (Rupe rearrangement) followed by a 6-*endo*-trig ring closure (Donnelly-Farrell cyclization) (Scheme 20). The isolation of the α,β -unsaturated ketone intermediate **45** is one example of the above pathway (Scheme 21).

Scheme 18. Synthesis of dibenzo[*b,g*][1,8]naphthyridin-5-ones.

Scheme 19. Synthesis of 2-substituted 2,3-dihydro-1*H*-quinolin-4-ones.

Scheme 20. Proposed mechanism for the acid-catalyzed cyclization.

Scheme 21. Isolation of α,β -unsaturated ketone intermediate.

A superacid can be prepared *in situ* by the combination of two components, a strong Lewis acid and a strong Brønsted acid²³. Dong and co-workers reported a regioselective β -lactam ring-opening/recyclization reaction of *N*-aryl-3-spirocyclic- β -lactams **46**, prepared by a one-pot cyclization reaction of acetoacetanilides using a Lewis-Brønsted acids combined superacid catalyst system. This provides an efficient entry to 3-spirocyclicquinolin-4(1*H*)-ones **47** (Scheme 22)²⁴. A mechanism involving superacid-catalysis has been proposed (Scheme 23). The superacid $\text{H}[\text{Fe}(\text{OTf})\text{Cl}_3]$ is first formed by combination of FeCl_3 and HOTf and then reacts with the substrate **46** to give

protonated intermediates **I–III**. Following the C–N bond cleavage, which is consistent with previously reported acid-catalyzed, *N*-protonated, unimolecular mechanism that might be involved in the rate-limiting step²⁵, an acylium ion **IV** is formed. The mechanism is favoured due to the enhanced rate of C–N bond cleavage that occurs in 2-azetidiones, resulting from the relief in ring strain. The highly reactive acyl carbonium ion **IV** then reacts with the aromatic unit, providing the desired 3-spirocyclicquinolin-4(1*H*)-one **47** through an intra-molecular acyl migration, with the release of catalyst $\text{H}[\text{Fe}(\text{OTf})\text{Cl}_3]$ for the next cycle.

Scheme 22. Lewis-Brønsted acids combined superacid catalyzed synthesis of quinoline derivatives.

Scheme 23. Proposed mechanism.

Scheme 27. The proposed mechanism of domino Povarov reaction.

Scheme 28. Synthesis of biquinoline quinoline-bearing chromene derivatives.

Scheme 29. Polyphosphoric acid-catalyzed quinoline synthesis.

Scheme 30. Chiral Brønsted acid-catalyzed inverse electron-demand aza-Diels-Alder reaction.

Scheme 31. An inverse electron-demand aza-Diels-Alder reaction.

catalytic sequential Povarov reaction/intramolecular hydroamination reaction by using a gold(I)/Brønsted acid binary system for the synthesis of polycyclic heterocycles. The three-component cascade reaction of 2-(2-propynyl)aniline derivatives **68**, aldehyde **10** and enecarbamates **65** consists of an enantioselective [4 + 2] cycloaddition reaction catalyzed by chiral phosphoric acid **63** and a subsequent catalytic intramolecular hydroamination by a gold(I) complex **69**. This approach provides a unique method for the preparation of structurally diverse and complex julolidine derivatives **70** in high optical purity (Scheme 32)³⁴. Kinetic studies revealed that the phosphoric acid is not only a chiral catalyst for the Povarov reaction but also an activator for the gold complex-catalyzed hydroamination reaction.

ing substituents as well as electron-donating substituents in *ortho*-, *meta*- and *para*-positions were appropriate substrates, affording the products in good yields with excellent diastereo- and enantioselectivity (up to 99% ee). However, a complex mixture was obtained with linear aliphatic aldehydes. Both electron-rich and electron-deficient *para*-substituted anilines participated to give products in good yields and enantioselectivities. Remarkably, when a substituent in the *meta*-position was present on the aniline, the cycloaddition led only to the formation of the more congested regioisomer.

The same group also developed another three-component Povarov reaction using enethioureas **74** as dienophile and chiral phosphoric acid catalyst **72** where they were

Scheme 32. Synthesis of julolidines by cascade reactions under relay catalysis.

Recently Masson group made use of the inverse electron-demand aza-Diels-Alder reaction for a wide variety of 2,3,4-trisubstituted tetrahydroquinoline derivatives **73** containing an aryl group at the 4-position³⁵. This one-pot, chiral phosphoric acid **72**-catalyzed highly enantio- and diastereoselective three component reaction afforded the desired products in good to high yields and excellent stereoselectivities (>95:5 dr and up to >99% ee) (Scheme 33). Aromatic aldehydes with electron-withdraw-

able to overcome their aforesaid difficulties (Scheme 34)³⁶.

Gold(I)/Brønsted acid combined catalytic system were used by Che and co-workers for efficient one-pot asymmetric synthesis of tetrahydroquinoline derivatives **76** from the reaction of aminobenzaldehydes or aminophenones **1** with alkynes **38**³⁷. This process (Scheme 35) provides a highly efficient method for the synthesis of optically active tetrahydroquinolines, with one or two chiral centres at different positions, as well as highly divergent func-

Scheme 33. Chiral phosphoric acid-catalyzed IEDDA.

Scheme 34. Enantioselective Povarov reaction using enethiouras as dienophile.

Scheme 35. Gold(I)/Brønsted acid cooperative system catalyzed synthesis of quinoline derivatives.

tional groups from simple starting materials via independent tenability of catalyst components in good to excellent yields and with high regio-, diastereo- and enantioselectivities.

Very recently, Tu's group developed the first chiral phosphoric acid **72**-catalyzed asymmetric isatin-involved Povarov reaction³⁸. The reaction between isatins **79**, substituted anilines **14** and α -methyl *o*-hydroxystyrenes **80**

provides an unprecedented approach to access the enantioenriched spiro[indolin-3,2'-quinoline] scaffolds **81** of medical relevance with concomitant creation of two quaternary stereogenic centers in high yields and excellent stereoselectivities (Scheme 36). Initially the *o*-hydroxystyrenes **80** participated in the vinylogous Mannich reaction with the ketimine generated from isatin **79** and aniline **14** catalyzed by chiral phosphoric acid **72** via a hydrogenbonding interaction, generating a transient intermediate I. This intermediate I subsequently underwent

an intramolecular Friedel-Crafts reaction facilitated by the same phosphoric acid **72**, to afford the enantioenriched spiro[indolin-3,2'-quinoline] derivatives **81** (Scheme 37).

Isoquinoline derivatives

Isoquinolines are important organic compounds due to their widespread occurrence in nature³⁹ and pharmacological applications⁴⁰. The use of tetrahydroisoquinolines

Scheme 36. Chiral phosphoric acid-catalyzed synthesis of spiro[indolin-3,2'-quinoline] derivatives.

Scheme 37. Proposed reaction mechanism.

as calcium antagonists⁴¹, antibacterial⁴² and antitumor antibiotics⁴³, or in cardiovascular diseases⁴⁴ has been reported. A typical example of a tetrahydroisoquinoline with therapeutic properties is 1-methyltetrahydroisoquinoline, a simple compound with activity against endogenous Parkinson's disease⁴⁵. Several tetrahydroisoquinoline derivatives were found to possess some neurochemical properties as MPTP. These derivatives may act

as neurotoxin precursors to active neurotoxins. Consequently, much attention has been paid to the development of efficient syntheses of a range of substituted isoquinoline derivatives.

Among various known methods (Scheme 38), the Pomeranz-Fritsch and Pictet-Spengler reactions are acid-catalyzed reaction, providing an efficient method for the preparation of isoquinoline derivatives.

Scheme 38. General known methods for acid-catalyzed synthesis of isoquinoline derivatives.

Among the recent acid-promoted isoquinoline syntheses Saito *et al.* used perfluorooctanesulfonic acid (PFOSA), Brønsted acid-surfactant-combined catalyst for efficient synthesis of isoquinoline derivatives **83**⁴⁶. The Pictet-Spengler reactions of β -arylethyl carbamate derivatives **82** with aldehydes **10** in water is accelerated by the addition of 1,1,1,3,3,3-hexafluoro-2-propanol (HFIP) (Scheme 39).

1-Vinylisoindolines and isoquinolines **86** have been synthesized by N.-Vázquez and co-workers starting from *N*-(ω -phenylalkyl)allenamides **84**⁴⁷. In presence of a catalytic amount of TFA, **84** can yield stabilized acyliminium ions **85** which via intramolecular aromatic electrophilic substitution furnish the desired product (Scheme 40). After synthesizing isoquinoline derivatives by this methodology, tetracyclic unit of the protoberberine skeleton **87** can easily be constructed by a 6-*exo* Heck reaction of an *ortho*-iodobenzamide.

Shin *et al.* used AgOTf and TfoH co-catalyzed redox reaction of readily available and hydrolytically stable *o*-alkyl oximes **88** for simple and efficient synthesis of isoquinoline derivatives **89**⁴⁸. Under AgOTf and Brønsted acid co-catalysis, *o*-alkynylbenzaldoxime derivatives undergo a cyclization-induced N-O cleavage to produce isoquinolines which are tolerant of various functional groups with the simultaneous oxidation of O-alkyl group (Scheme 41). Among various reactions, the (*E*)-ketoxime derivatives cyclized efficiently but the (*Z*)-ketoxime remained unchanged even after 3 h at 70 °C, indicating that (*E*)-geometry is required for the redox cyclization. Electron-donating -OMe group had a similar or slightly increased rate of the cyclization, while nitro group showed a slightly diminished reaction rate.

A novel and efficient method for the synthesis of C-4 unsubstituted isoquinoline **91** via Ag-catalyzed cyclization of 2-alkynylbenzyl azides **90** was reported by Liang

Scheme 39. Brønsted acid-surfactant-combined catalyst for isoquinoline synthesis.

Scheme 40. TFA-catalyzed synthesis of isoquinoline derivatives.

Scheme 41. Redox-mediated isoquinoline synthesis.

and co-workers⁴⁹. The use of Brønsted acid additive such as TFA is necessary to obtain the desired product in high yields (Scheme 42).

Scheme 42. Cyclization of *o*-iodoalkynylbenzyl azides.

Carboline derivatives

β -Carbolines, including its reduced derivatives, represent a large group of biologically active indole alkaloids widespread in nature⁵⁰. For example, Jadiffine⁵¹ and Neonaucleoside C⁵² were isolated from *Vinca difformis* and *Neonauclea sessilifolia*, respectively. Lavendamycin is a naturally occurring antitumor antibiotic which possesses cytotoxic properties and exhibits significant activity against topoisomerases (Fig. 1)⁵³. β -Carbolines also act as useful intermediates for natural product synthesis⁵⁴. As a consequence, much attention has been paid to the synthesis of β -carboline derivatives⁵⁵. The most common strategy is by the Pictet-Spengler reaction⁵⁶. Others

include, for example, ring derivatizations⁵⁷, metal- or Lewis acid-catalyzed intramolecular nucleophilic cyclization at the C-3 position of indole⁵⁸, copper-catalyzed C-N bond coupling reactions⁵⁹, Ru-catalyzed [2 + 2 + 2] cycloaddition of an electron-deficient nitrile to an alkyne⁶⁰ etc.

Seayad *et al.* developed a catalytic asymmetric Pictet-Spengler reaction which furnishes enantioenriched tetrahydro- β -carbolines **94** from various tryptamines **92**, aldehydes **10** and chiral Brønsted acid catalyst **93**⁶¹. The reaction (Scheme 43) tolerates a variety of different aldehydes with good results. Accordingly, both aliphatic unbranched aldehydes and branched aldehydes gave the products in reasonable to excellent yields.

Recently, Cook and co-workers showed that just by changing the condition of the experiment two different products **96** and **97** can be obtained from the substrate enamino **95**. The enamino **95** under Brønsted acid catalysis afforded the core tetracyclic framework **96** of the *Strychnos* alkaloids in optically active form. Alternatively the enamino **95** gave β -ketoester tetrahydro- β -carboline (THBC) unit **97** by varying the equivalents of acid and the molar concentration (Scheme 44)⁶².

Scheme 43. Synthesis of enantioenriched tetrahydro- β -carbolines.

Scheme 44. Acid-mediated cyclization of enamino.

The synthesis of fully substituted 1,2-dihydro- β -carbolines **100** has been developed by Liu *et al.* via Brønsted acid (TfOH)-mediated cyclization of α -indolyl propargylic alcohols **98** with nitrones **99** (Scheme 45)⁶³. The use of nitrones bearing an electron-rich C-aryl ring or C-alkenyl group dramatically switches the reaction pathway to afford tetrasubstituted alkenes and amines, which is assumed to proceed through a rearrangement reaction involving N-O bond cleavage and 1,2-migration (Scheme 46). The results seem to be of importance for the development of new reactions with the use of nitrones.

heterocyclizations. Brønsted acids have been shown to efficiently catalyze the intramolecular addition of nitrogen nucleophiles to alkynes, allenes and olefins to generate nitrogen heterocycles. Moreover, numerous natural and unnatural products based on quinoline, isoquinoline and carboline have been prepared by synthetic routes that have a Brønsted acid-promoted cyclization as a crucial step. Brønsted acid has also been used as co-catalysts with other transition metals. Unique activity was found for these Brønsted acid-based systems in several cases.

Scheme 45. TfOH-mediated cyclization.

Scheme 46. Possible reaction mechanism.

Conclusion

Significant progress has been made during the past several years, in the exploration of Brønsted acid-based

Consequently, the use of Brønsted acid can enrich several available heterocyclization methods for the synthesis of quinoline, isoquinoline and carboline derivatives.

Acknowledgement

We thank UGC (New Delhi) for Emeritus Fellowship (KCM) and CSIR (New Delhi) for Senior Research Fellowship (SP).

References

- (a) Y. Morimoto, F. Matsuda and H. Shirahama, *Synlett*, 1991, 202; (b) M. Balasubramanian and J. G. Keay, in "Comprehensive Heterocyclic Chemistry II", eds. A. R. Katritzky, C. W. Rees and E. F. V. Scriven, Pergamon, New York, 1996, Vol. 5, p. 245; (c) J. P. Michael, *Nat. Prod. Rep.*, 1997, 14, 605.
- (a) D. G. Markees, V. C. Dewey and G. W. Kidder, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1970, 13, 324; (b) S. F. Campbell, J. D. Hardstone and M. J. Palmer, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1988, 31, 1031; (c) M. P. Maguire, K. R. Sheets, K. Mcvety, A. P. Spada and A. Zilberstein, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1994, 37, 2129; (d) B. Kalluraya and S. Sreenivasa, *Il Farmaco*, 1998, 53, 399; (e) G. Roma, M. D. Braccio, G. Grossi, F. Mattioli and M. Ghia, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2000, 35, 1021; (f) Y.-L. Chen, K.-C. Fang, J.-Y. Sheu, S.-L. Hsu and C.-C. Tzeng, *J. Med. Chem.*, 2001, 44, 2374.
- (a) E. Elslager, F. Tendick and L. Werbel, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1969, 12, 600; (b) M. Czarniecki, *J. Med. Chem.*, 2008, 51, 6621; (c) A. Halama, J. Jirman, O. Boušková, P. Gibala and K. Jarrah, *Org. Process Res. Dev.*, 2010, 14, 425; (d) G. Shanks, A. Oloo, G. Aleman, C. Ohrt, F. Klotz, D. Braitman, J. Horton and R. Brueckner, *Clin. Infect. Dis.*, 2001, 33, 1968.
- (a) C. H. Cheng, R. M. Chen, C. W. Huang and C. C. Yang, U.S. Patent 20050025995A1, 2005; (b) M. E. Thompson, B. Ma and P. Djurovich, U.S. Patent 20050164031A1, 2005; (c) D. B. Knowles and R. Kwong, U.S. Patent 20050164030A1, 2005; (e) J. L. Kim, I. S. Shin and H. Kim, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2005, 127, 1614.
- (a) I. Abrunhosa, L. Delain-Bioton, A. C. Gaumont, M. Gulea and S. Masson, *Tetrahedron*, 2004, 60, 9263; (b) Y. Zhang and M. S. Sigman, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2007, 129, 3076; (c) M. M. Biddle, M. Lin and K. A. Scheidt, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2007, 129, 3830; (d) B. Tan, Z. Shi, P. J. Chua and G. Zhong, *Org. Lett.*, 2008, 10, 3425.
- (a) A. R. Katritzky and M. Arend, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1998, 63, 9989; (b) S. Cacchi, G. Fabrizi and F. Marinelli, *Synlett*, 1999, 401; (c) M. Sugimoto, T. Fukuda and Y. Ito, *Org. Lett.*, 1999, 1, 1977; (d) B. C. Ranu, A. Hajra and U. Jana, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2000, 41, 531; (e) C. S. Cho, B. H. Oh, J. S. Kim, T.-J. Kim and S. C. Shim, *Chem. Commun.*, 2000, 1885; (f) M. Arisawa, C. Theeraladanon, A. Nishida and M. Nakagawa, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2001, 42, 8029; (g) B. Jiang and Y.-G. Si, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2002, 67, 9449; (h) M.-E. Theoclitou and L. A. Robinson, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2002, 43, 3907.
- (a) P. Friedländer, *Ber.*, 1882, 15, 2572; (b) C.-C. Cheng and S.-J. Yan, *Org. React.*, 1982, 28, 37.
- C.-S. Jia, Z. Zhang, S.-J. Tu and G.-W. Wang, *Org. Biomol. Chem.*, 2006, 4, 104.
- G.-W. Wang, C.-S. Jia and Y.-W. Dong, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2006, 47, 1059.
- A. Shaabani, E. Soleimani and Z. Badri, *Synth. Commun.*, 2007, 37, 629.
- For reviews, see : (a) H. Waldmann, *Synthesis*, 1994, 535; (b) A. R. Katritzky, S. Rachwal and B. Rachwal, *Tetrahedron*, 1996, 52, 15031; (c) K. A. Jørgensen, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.*, 2000, 39, 3558; (d) J. S. Johnson and D. A. Evans, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 2000, 33, 325; (e) P. Buonora, J.-C. Olsen and T. Oh, *Tetrahedron*, 2001, 57, 6099; (f) "Cycloaddition Reactions in Organic Synthesis", eds. S. Kobayashi and K. A. Jørgensen, Wiley-VCH, Weinheim, Germany, 2002.
- X. Xing, J. Wu and W.-M. Dai, *Tetrahedron*, 2006, 62, 11200; (b) R. H. Liu, X. Yu, L. Hu and N. F. Yu, *Chin. Chem. Lett.*, 2012, 9, 1027.
- M. M. Tomashevskaya, O. A. Tomashenko, A. A. Tomashevskii, V. V. Sokolov and A. A. Potekhin, *Russ. J. Org. Chem.*, 2007, 43, 75.
- M. J. Sandelier and P. Deshong, *Org. Lett.*, 2007, 9, 3209.
- S. Some and J. K. Ray, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2007, 48, 5013.
- Y. Wang, C. Peng, L. Liu, Z. Zhao, L. Su and Q. Zhu, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2009, 50, 2261.
- H. Liu, G. Dagousset, G. Masson, P. Retailleau and J. Zhu, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2009, 131, 4598.
- K. C. Majumdar, A. Taher and S. Ponra, *Synlett*, 2010, 735.
- C. G. Evans and J. E. Gestwicki, *Org. Lett.*, 2009, 11, 2957.
- M. M. Heravi, M. Saedi, N. Karimi, M. Zakeri, Y. S. Beheshtiha and A. Davoodnia, *Synth. Commun.*, 2007, 37, 629.
- M. Zhang, T. Roisnel and P. H. Dixneuf, *Adv. Synth. Catal.*, 2010, 11-12, 1896.
- M. Manoj and K. J. R. Prasad, *Synth. Commun.*, 2010, 40, 3290.
- F. Pisaneschi, J. J. P. Sejberg, C. Blain, W. H. Ng, E. O. Aboagye and A. C. Spivey, *Synlett*, 2011, 241.
- V. V. Kouznetsov, *J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 2005, 42, 39.
- Y. Hu, X. Fu, B.-D. Barry, X. Bi and D. Dong, *Chem. Commun.*, 2012, 48, 690.
- M. V. Roux, P. Jimenez, J. Z. Davalos, O. Castano, M. T. Molina, R. Notario, M. Herreros and J.-L. M. Abboud, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1996, 118, 12735.
- A. Rajendran, C. Karthikeyan, K. Rajathi and D. Ragupathy, *J. Chem. Sci.*, 2012, 124, 877.
- M. G. Kulkarni, M. P. Desai, D. R. Birahade, Y. B.

- Shaikh, A. N. Dhatrak and R. Gannamani, *Beilstein J. Org. Chem.*, 2012, **8**, 1725.
28. J. Sun, H. Gao, Q. Wu and C.-G. Yan, *Beilstein J. Org. Chem.*, 2012, **8**, 1839.
29. M. Sankaran, K. Chandraprakash, C. Uvarani, K. N. Vennila, D. Velmurugan and P. S. Mohan, *Synlett*, 2012, 2858.
30. M. Shiri, M. A. Zolfigol, M. Priveysian, R. Ayazi-Nasrabadi, H. G. Kruger, T. Naicker and I. Mohammadpoor-Baltork, *Tetrahedron*, 2012, **68**, 6059.
31. (a) H. Waldmann, *Synthesis*, 1994, 535; (b) A. R. Katritzky, S. Rachwal and B. Rachwal, *Tetrahedron*, 1996, **52**, 15031; (c) K. A. Jørgensen, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.*, 2000, **39**, 3558; (d) J. S. Johnson and D. A. Evans, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 2000, **33**, 325; (e) P. Buonora, J.-C. Olsen and T. Oh, *Tetrahedron*, 2001, **57**, 6099.
32. T. Akiyama, H. Morita and K. Fuchibe, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2006, **128**, 13070.
33. (a) H. Liu, G. Dagousset, G. Masson, P. Retailleau and J. Zhu, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2009, **131**, 4598; (b) G. Dagousset, J. Zhu and G. Masson, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2011, **133**, 14804.
34. C. Wang, Z.-Y. Han, H.-W. Luo and L.-Z. Gong, *Org. Lett.*, 2010, **12**, 2266.
35. L. He, M. Bekkaye, P. Retailleau and G. Masson, *Org. Lett.*, 2012, **14**, 3158.
36. G. Dagousset, P. Retailleau, G. Masson and J. Zhu, *Chem.-Eur. J.*, 2012, **18**, 5869.
37. X.-Y. Liu, Y.-P. Xiao, F.-M. Siu, L.-C. Ni, Y. Chen, L. Wang and C.-M. Che, *Org. Biomol. Chem.*, 2012, **10**, 7208.
38. F. Shi, G.-J. Xing, R.-Y. Zhu, W. Tan and S. Tu, *Org. Lett.*, 2013, **15**, 128.
39. (a) K. W. Bentley, *Nat. Prod. Rep.*, 2003, **20**, 342; (b) J. D. Scott and R. M. Williams, *Chem. Rev.*, 2002, **102**, 1669; (c) M. D. Rozwadowska, *Heterocycles*, 1994, **39**, 903; (d) M. Chrzanowska and M. D. Rozwadowska, *Chem. Rev.*, 2004, **104**, 3341; (e) J. L. Vicario, D. Badia, L. Carrillo and J. Etchebarria, *Curr. Org. Chem.*, 2003, **7**, 1775.
40. (a) R. B. Herbert, in "The Chemistry and Biology of Isoquinoline Alkaloids", eds. J. D. Philipson, M. F. Roberts and M. H. Zenk, Springer-Verlag, Berlin, 1985, p. 213; (b) M. Samma, in "Isoquinoline Alkaloids, Chemistry and Pharmacology", Academic Press, New York, 1972.
41. H. Dong, J. Z. Sheng and T. M. Wong, *Br. J. Pharmacol.*, 1993, **109**, 113.
42. S. Chandrasekhar, P. K. Mohanty, K. Harikishan and P. K. Sasmal, *Org. Lett.*, 1999, **1**, 877.
43. J. D. Scott and R. M. Williams, *Chem. Rev.*, 2002, **102**, 1669.
44. H. Dong, C. M. Lee, W. L. Huang and S. X. Peng, *Br. J. Pharmacol.*, 1992, **107**, 262.
45. K. Ishiwata, Y. Koyanagi, K. Abe, K. Kawamura, K. Taguchi, T. Saitoh, J. Toda, M. Senda and T. J. Sano, *Neurochem.*, 2001, **79**, 868.
46. A. Saito, J. Numaguchi and Y. Hanawa, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2007, **48**, 835.
47. A. N. Vázquez, D. Rodríguez, M. F. Martínez-Esperón, A. García, C. Saá and D. Domínguez, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2007, **48**, 2741.
48. S. Hwang, Y. Lee, P. H. Lee and S. Shin, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2009, **50**, 2305.
49. Y.-N. Niu, Z.-Y. Yan, G.-L. Gao, H.-L. Wang, X.-Z. Shu, K.-G. Ji and Y.-M. Liang, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2009, **74**, 2893.
50. (a) "Introduction to Alkaloids : A Biogenetic Approach", ed. G. A. Cordell, Wiley, New York, 1981; (b) "Comprehensive Natural Products Chemistry", eds. D. E. Cane, D. H. R. Barton, K. Nakanishi, O. Meth-Cohn and J. W. Kelly, Elsevier, New York, 1999; (c) B. J. Magnier and Y. Langlois, *Tetrahedron*, 1998, **54**, 6201; (d) J. E. Saxton, *Nat. Prod. Rep.*, 1997, 559; (e) H. Wang, T. Usui, H. Osada and A. Ganesan, *J. Med. Chem.*, 2000, **43**, 1577; (f) S. K. Srivastava, A. Agarwal, P. M. S. Chauhan, S. K. Agarwal, A. P. Bhaduri, S. N. Singh, N. Fatima and R. K. Chatterjee, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1999, **42**, 1667; (g) H. Zhang and R. C. Larock, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2002, **67**, 7048; (h) C. A. Busacca and Y. Dong, *Synth. Commun.*, 2000, **30**, 501; (i) A. Madrigal, M. Grande and C. Avendano, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1998, **63**, 2724; (j) C.-B. Cui, H. Kakeya and H. Osada, *Tetrahedron*, 1997, **53**, 59; (k) G. Wu, E. Yamamaka and J. Cook, *Heterocycles*, 1978, **9**, 175.
51. J. Garnier, J. Mahuteau, M. Plat and C. Merienne, *Phytochemistry*, 1989, **28**, 308.
52. A. Itoh, T. Tanahashi, N. Nagakura and T. Nishi, *Phytochemistry*, 2003, **62**, 359.
53. D. L. Boger, M. Yasuda, L. A. Mitscher, S. D. Drake, P. A. Kitos and S. C. Thompson, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1987, **30**, 1918.
54. (a) P. Yu, T. Wang, J. Li and J. M. Cook, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2000, **65**, 3173; (b) H. Zhou, X. Liao and J. M. Cook, *Org. Lett.*, 2004, **6**, 249; (c) C. Liu, M. N. Masuno, J. B. MacMillan and T. F. Molinski, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.*, 2004, **43**, 5951; (d) T. Yamashita, N. Kawai, H. Tokuyama and T. Fukuyama, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2005, **127**, 15038; (e) J. Yu, X. Z. Wearing and J. M. Cook, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2005, **70**, 3963; (f) H. Zhou, D. Han, X. Liao and J. M. Cook, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2005, **46**, 4219; (g) H. Zhou, X. Liao, W. Yin, J. Ma and J. M. Cook, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2006, **71**, 251; (h) J. Ma, W. Yin, H. Zhou and J. M. Cook, *Org. Lett.*, 2007, **9**, 3491; (i) D. J. Mergott, S.

- J. Zuend and E. N. Jacobsen, *Org. Lett.*, 2008, **10**, 745.
55. For review, see : B. E. Love, *Org. Prep. Proc. Int.*, 1996, **28**, 1.
56. For reviews, see : (a) E. D. Cox and J. M. Cook, *Chem. Rev.*, 1995, **95**, 1797; (b) J. Stöckigt, A. P. Antonchick, F. Wu and H. Waldmann, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.*, 2011, **50**, 8538; Recent reports : (c) T. Arai, M. Wasai and N. Yokoyama, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2011, **76**, 2909; (d) M. S. Taylor and E. N. Jacobsen, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2004, **126**, 10558; (e) J. Seayad, A. M. Seayad and B. List, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2006, **128**, 1086.
57. (a) M. Nakagawa, T. Kawate, H. Yamazaki and T. Hino, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1990, 991; (b) C. A. Busacca, M. C. Eriksson, Y. Dong, A. S. Prokopowicz, A. M. Salvagno and M. A. Tschantz, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1999, **64**, 4564; (c) C. Rannoux, F. Roussi, P. Retailleau and F. Gueritte, *Org. Lett.*, 2010, **12**, 1240.
58. (a) M. Agnusdei, M. Bandini, A. Melloni and A. Umani-Ronchi, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2003, **68**, 7126; (b) M. Bandini, A. Melloni, F. Piccinelli, R. Sinisi, S. Tommasi and A. Umani-Ronchi, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2006, **128**, 1424; (c) D. B. England and A. Padwa, *Org. Lett.*, 2008, **10**, 3631; (d) Y. Ohta, H. Chiba, S. Oishi, N. Fujii and H. Ohno, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2009, **74**, 7052.
59. W. Schlecker, A. Huth, E. Ottow and J. Mulzer, *Tetrahedron*, 1995, **51**, 9531.
60. F. Nissen and H. Detert, *Eur. J. Org. Chem.*, 2011, **76**, 2845.
61. J. Seayad, A. M. Seayad and B. List, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2006, **128**, 1086.
62. R. V. Edwankar, C. R. Edwankar, O. A. Namjoshi, J. R. Deschamps and J. M. Cook, *J. Nat. Prod.*, 2012, **75**, 181.
63. L. Wang, X. Xie and Y. Liu, *Org. Lett.*, 2012, **14**, 5848.